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ANALYSIS OF AUTOMATION THROUGH MOISTURE MONITORING DEVICES IN INDUSTRIAL AND AGRICULTURAL FIELDS

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Abstract. This article explores the pivotal role of moisture monitoring device in the automation of industrial and agricultural practices. It provides an in-depth analysis of three primary types of Moisture monitoring device - Capacitive, Resistive, and Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR) - and discusses their respective principles, benefits, and limitations. Moisture monitoring device are integral to the automation of agricultural and industrial processes, offering significant benefits in resource management and productivity. Capacitive, Resistive, and TDR sensors each serve specific needs, from cost-effective solutions to high-precision applications. As technology advances, these sensors will increasingly drive sustainable and efficient practices in various fields, making them essential tools for future automation strategies.

In addition, we will explore the different aspects of moisture monitoring device using software to analyze and manage the upcoming changes. It is important to analyze the role of such sensors in industrial and agricultural areas and to study solutions. In today's automated processes, it is necessary to ensure that all sensors and systems work without problems.

Keywords: Humidity, algorithm, robotics, sensor, moisture monitoring device, agriculture.

Introduction. Modern agricultural technologies rely heavily on moisture monitoring device to conserve water resources, boost productivity, and maintain plant health. these tools accurately gauge soil water content levels, helping farmers to determine the precise watering needs of their crops. in addition to exploring the technical aspects of moisture monitoring device, such as measurement precision, durability, and installation procedures, this discourse also delves into the pros and cons of various sensor technologies like capacitive, resistive, and TDR. while capacitive sensors offer affordability and simplicity, their effectiveness hinges on soil composition. on the other hand, resistive sensors excel at detecting moisture levels but may suffer from corrosion over time. TDR sensors, though costly, deliver superior accuracy and consistent performance across diverse soil types.

Applications of moisture monitoring device in agriculture and scientific research, such as climate change adaptation and water conservation strategies, are discussed. the integration of soil water content monitoring systems using advanced software and IOT technologies is also explored, enabling real-time data collection and analysis to facilitate precise irrigation decisions. a Moisture monitoring device is utilized to measure the soil's moisture content, aiding in the automation of soil water content level monitoring for various crops.

Understanding the soil water content is essential for optimizing irrigation practices and ensuring the proper growth and development of crops. By accurately measuring the moisture levels in the soil, farmers can make informed decisions on when and how much water to apply to the crops. This not only helps in conserving water but also in preventing

waterlogging, which can lead to root rot and other issues.

The advancements in soil water content sensing technology have made it easier for farmers to monitor the soil conditions in real time and make adjustments as needed. These sensors can be connected to a central system for remote monitoring, allowing farmers to access the data from anywhere at any time. This level of automation and precision in monitoring soil water content levels is revolutionizing the way agriculture is practiced, leading to higher crop yields and better resource management.

In addition to monitoring soil water content levels, these sensors can also help in detecting other soil properties such as temperature and salinity. This comprehensive data can provide valuable insights into the overall health of the soil and help in making informed decisions on crop management practices. As the technology continues to evolve, we can expect even more advanced sensors that can provide even more detailed and accurate information for sustainable and efficient farming practices. The future of agriculture lies in harnessing the power of technology, and moisture monitoring device are at the forefront of this transformation.

Literature analysis and methods. Soil water content is a critical parameter in agriculture, hydrology, and environmental management. Accurate soil water content measurement aids in optimizing irrigation, enhancing crop yields, and managing water resources efficiently. This article reviews the existing literature on moisture monitoring device and discusses the methods used for their evaluation and application.

Charles W. Rose's research focused on soil hydrology and the development of capacitance and resistance-based moisture monitoring device. He published extensively on the theoretical and practical aspects of soil water content sensing. Calibration involves comparing neutron probe readings with gravimetric soil water content measurements in controlled conditions. Validation extends this comparison to field conditions across various soil types and moisture ranges. Richard G. Allen has contributed significantly to the field of remote sensing of soil water

content. He has worked on integrating ground-based sensor data with satellite observations to improve soil water content estimation.

They are combining ground-based sensor data with satellite observations to estimate soil water content over large areas. Methods include validating satellite data with field measurements.

The field of soil water content sensing has advanced significantly thanks to the contributions of many dedicated researchers. Their work on developing, calibrating, and validating various sensor technologies has laid the groundwork for modern soil water content monitoring systems. Continuous innovation and interdisciplinary collaboration are essential for further advancements, particularly in integrating these sensors with emerging technologies like IoT and machine learning.

Discussion.

When considering the construction of a smart irrigation or automated plant watering system, the Moisture monitoring device is often the first component that comes to mind. By integrating this sensor with an Arduino, we can create a system that efficiently waters your plants at the appropriate times, preventing both overwatering and underwatering.

In this article, we will connect a Moisture monitoring device to an Arduino to assess the volumetric water content in the soil. This moisture sensor can provide readings in both digital and analog formats. We will process these readings and indicate the output status using an LED for digital signals, while analog signals will be displayed either on the serial monitor or via LED with PWM control. It's important to note that the Moisture monitoring device is also referred to as a soil humidity sensor, and we will use these terms interchangeably throughout the text.

This Moisture monitoring device, or soil humidity sensor, consists of four pins: VCC, GND, Aout, and Dout, all of which facilitate the acquisition of moisture data directly from the sensor.

The operation of the Moisture monitoring device is quite straightforward, as illustrated in the image below. To use it, simply insert the fork-shaped conductive probe into the soil. This probe features two

exposed conductive plates that function as a variable resistor, with its resistance changing based on the soil's water content.

The probe's resistance is inversely related to moisture levels; higher water content leads to better conductivity and consequently lower resistance, while lower water content results in poorer conductivity and higher resistance. This Arduino sensor outputs a voltage that corresponds to the measured resistance, allowing us to assess the moisture level.

Figure 1. The pinout of the Moisture monitoring device.

- VCC is the power supply pin, which can connect to either 3.3V or 5V. Keep in mind that the analog output will differ based on the voltage supplied.
- GND refers to the ground pin of the board that should be linked to the Arduino's ground.
- DOUT is the digital output pin; a low output suggests adequate soil water content, while a high output indicates low moisture levels.
- AOUT is the analog output pin that provides a continuous signal between VCC and ground.

Analog to Digital conversion:

$$\text{Analog Read output} = (\text{Input Voltage} / \text{Maximum Voltage}) * 1024$$

Note: Arduino Uno supports 10-bit ADC, Which means the resolution of the output is $2^{10} = 1024$.

We can notice that the sensor reading output goes up to a maximum of Analog value: 876.

Here we are applying 5 Volts to the VCC pin of the sensor, For 5 Volts, we are getting a maximum of

4.28 Volts Approximately in the SIG pin (output pin). Its equivalent ADC value is 876.

$$\text{Calculation: } (4.28 / 5) * 1024 = 876$$

So the output varies from 0 to 876.

Note: This range may change based on the hardware manufacturer. Analyze before using the limits.

In terms of the Arduino code for the Moisture monitoring device, it is quite simple. We read the sensor's analog data and adjust the brightness of an LED based on this information. Initially, we define two macros: one for the LED and another for the detectorpin to read data.

```
int lamppinn=6;
int detectorpin=A0;
```

Next, we have our **setup()** function. In the setup routine, we begin by configuring the serial communication at a 9600 baud rate. We also define the lampPin as an output and set the pin to LOW. This ensures the pin won't float and accidentally activate the LED.

```
void setup() {
  Serial.begin(9600);
  pinMode(lamppinn, OUTPUT);
  digitalWrite(lamppinn, LOW);
}
```

Next, we have our **loop()** function, in the loop function we print "Continuous signal:" as text on the serial monitor window and then we call the **measure_sensor_output()** function inside a **Serial.println()** function so that once the **measure_sensor_output()** function is executed, it returns the data and it also gets printed on the serial monitor window,

```
void loop() {
  Serial.print("Continuous signal: ");
  Serial.println(measure_sensor_output());
  delay(500);
}
```

We have developed a custom function, **measure_sensor_output()**, that reads the analog signal from the A0 pin on the Arduino. Within this function,

we start by declaring and defining a variable called `detectorValue` to store the raw input collected from the A0 pin. This input is represented in a 10-bit range, spanning from 0 to 1023. To convert this 10-bit data into an 8-bit format, we make use of the `*map*` function. Once the map function processes the data, we assign the modified value to another variable named `out_Val`. Afterward, we utilize the built-in `analogWrite(lamppinn, out_Val)` function on the Arduino to generate a PWM signal, which reflects the input data captured by the Arduino's ADC.

This concludes the coding section for the Arduino-based moisture monitoring device project. If you have any inquiries related to the code, please feel free to leave your questions in the comments below.

```
int measure_sensor_output() {  
    int detectorValue = analogRead(detectorpin);  
    int out_Val = map(detectorValue, 0, 1023,  
255, 0);  
    analogWrite(lamppinn, out_Val);  
    return out_Val;  
}
```

It works, when electrical currents are sent through the legs of the moisture sensor. The sensor then calculates the resistance it's getting. Since water conducts electricity - the wetter the soil is, the less resistance there should be. It's then connected to an Analog Pin and the Arduino can use that for the program.

The Moisture monitoring device needs to know the maximum moisture that the soil can reach, so we can calculate the percentages. This is called calibration. The sensor calibrates right when the circuit is switched on, in the `Setup()` function. Therefore, it should already be in freshly watered soil, when it is switched on.

Results. We can write software code to use the Moisture monitoring device. We can write the software code in C++ or Python programming languages. During the writing of the program, it is important to control its correct and accurate operation.

```
void setup()  
{  
    Serial.begin(9600);
```

```
pinMode(13, OUTPUT);  
pinMode(12, OUTPUT);  
pinMode(11, OUTPUT);  
pinMode(10, OUTPUT);  
pinMode(9, OUTPUT);  
}  
void loop()  
{  
    int s_m_sensor;  
    s_m_sensor = analogRead(0);  
    Serial.println("Analog value:");  
    Serial.println(s_m_sensor);  
  
    digitalWrite(13, LOW);  
    digitalWrite(12, LOW);  
    digitalWrite(11, LOW);  
    digitalWrite(10, LOW);  
    digitalWrite(9, LOW);  
  
    if (s_m_sensor < 175) {  
        digitalWrite(13, HIGH);  
    }  
    else if (s_m_sensor < 350) {  
        digitalWrite(12, HIGH);  
    }  
    else if (s_m_sensor < 525) {  
        digitalWrite(11, HIGH);  
    }  
    else if (s_m_sensor < 700) {  
        digitalWrite(10, HIGH);  
    }  
    else if (s_m_sensor < 876) {  
        digitalWrite(9, HIGH);  
    }  
}
```

When developing a software application, it is essential to consider all possible scenarios. Our automated systems may experience failures if there are software inaccuracies. After confirming the correct values, we must configure the automated systems accordingly to ensure they function effectively.

Figure 2. The condition of connecting the Moisture monitoring device to the microcontroller.

The diagram illustrates the use of Arduino, but this Moisture monitoring device can also be implemented with other programming platforms and microcontrollers. Throughout our research on the Moisture monitoring device's parameters, we conducted tests using devices such as the ESP32, Arduino Nano, Arduino Mega, and Raspberry Pi. In these experiments, we examined how the sensor and the accompanying software interact, as well as the data they produce.

Figure 3. The state of connecting the Moisture monitoring device to the microcontroller, outputting the moisture value.

Capacitance involves a sensor that utilizes the soil as a capacitor, relying on its ability to store charge to determine water content. Time-domain reflectometry (TDR) measures the duration it takes for an electrical signal to bounce back along a transmission line, with this timing linked to the soil's charge storage and volumetric water content. Notably, TDR signals

encompass a range of frequencies, helping to mitigate errors caused by soil salinity. Similarly, frequency-domain sensors (FDR) utilize the soil in a capacitive role to gauge the circuit's maximum resonant frequency and correlate it with water content.

	Resistance	TDR	Capacitance
Price	Lowest	Moderate to high	Low to moderate
Accuracy	Low	High* (with soil-specific calibration)	High* (with soil-specific calibration)
Complexity	Easy	Easy to intermediate	Easy
Power use	Low	Moderate to high	Low
Salinity Sensitivity	Extreme	1. None in low to medium salinity. 2. Yes in high salinity	Yes in high salinity
Durability	Low	High	High
Volume of Influence	Small area between probe A and probe B	0.25 liter to 2 liters depending on probe length and shape of the electromagnetic field	0.25 liter to 2 liters depending on probe length and shape of the electromagnetic field

Table1. Analysis of results obtained from different moisture monitoring device.

Conclusion. In the quest for optimized resource utilization and enhanced productivity, the integration of Moisture monitoring device has become pivotal in both industrial and agricultural sectors. This article delves into the automation analysis facilitated by different types of Moisture monitoring device, namely Capacitive, Resistive, and Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR) sensors, highlighting their roles, benefits, and limitations.

Capacitive Sensors work by measuring changes in the dielectric constant of the soil. They are known for their non-corrosive nature and moderate accuracy, making them a durable and reliable choice for long-term use. Resistive Sensors measure soil water content

by detecting variations in electrical resistance between two probes inserted into the soil. While they are cost-effective and easy to use, their exposed metal parts are prone to corrosion, leading to a shorter lifespan and lower accuracy. TDR Sensors utilize electromagnetic pulse travel time to determine soil water content levels. These sensors offer high accuracy and are less affected by soil texture and density, though they come with a higher cost and complexity.

In general, as a result of analysis and experiments, many Moisture monitoring device have been studied. These sensors have been tested under different conditions and on different devices. Conclusions were drawn based on the general results of the solutions.

The adoption of Moisture monitoring device in industrial and agricultural fields represents a significant step towards automation and smart farming. By leveraging the strengths of Capacitive, Resistive, and TDR sensors, stakeholders can achieve better resource management, increased efficiency, and sustainable growth. As technology continues to advance, these sensors will play an increasingly critical role in the future of industrial and agricultural automation.

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